

WAYS TO DEVELOP SMALL BUSINESS SUBJECTS IN THE UZBEKISTAN

Ubayeva Sultanpashsha Saidkarimova

E-mail: ubayevasultana@gmail.com (Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology) (tel +998 99 393 19 20)
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807571>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th March 2023
Accepted: 06th April 2023
Online: 07th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Small business, property, investment, unemployment, incentives, competition, employment.

ABSTRACT

This in the article small business and private entrepreneurship development directions, small business national in the economy place and importance economic indicators through illuminated. Small business and private entrepreneurship market environment fast adapt getting, employment provide income formation and that's it through his inequality softening and medium the owners layer decision in finding advantages open given.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan small business and private of entrepreneurship development and this sector state by in order to be put more becoming active is going In the country entrepreneurship environment more and more expansion small business of subjects incentive based on activities to provide take is coming, almost all in networks small business subjects year after year amount in terms of increased is going

Small business and entrepreneurship the economy development, population employment increase, of the owners medium class formation, internal the market good quality and competitive products with filling, new the work places Create and that's it with together population income increase important factor and country development on the way active moving strength is considered

Our country in the area comfortable entrepreneurship environment create, private of ownership priority to strengthen directed the law documents improvement and this about reliable guarantees provide, small business and private to entrepreneurship more freedom to give, of the state management functions and permission giver norms reduction, bureaucratic obstacle and holes take throw, small business of subjects finance and credit and raw material of resources, they work emits to products state orders from being given wide to use which provides market tools and mechanisms application reach small business and private to entrepreneurship wide road to open measures as done by increasing is coming. That's it to emphasize OK, let 's go placed from reforms main the goal republic population entrepreneurship to the field wide in scope attraction to reach provide, produce release and service show in the field private of business role quality in terms of is to increase. Small

business and entrepreneurship development main reasons one population the number continuous respectively grow up is going.

Uzbekistan Republic President Mirziyoyev Shavkat Miromonovich as noted:

Our main task is entrepreneurship development encourage _ for the most comfortable conditions to create is to provide. Business with engaged in each in a person state by support diligently trust to be a must People business with from engaging interested to be necessary Entrepreneur and if the people are rich, the country will also be rich.

Of this at the expense of entrepreneurs 3.4 trillion uz at his disposal or past per year compared to 2.5 times a lot funds remain. For example, in our country small business and private entrepreneurship development via:

- medium the owners class is formed;

- macroeconomic instability, unemployment and shortage such as economic problems I'm done finds;

- healthy competition environment creation through of GDP amount and quality in terms of growth observed;

- internal market necessary with goods (services). is full and their quality increases;

- in the end population marriage level to the growth is achieved.

Small business and private entrepreneurship development not only state and public in development, perhaps every one of a person rise up going vital needs in satisfaction important important have, that is service display, retail trade, food products work release such as in the fields this activity obvious manifestation will be The same at the time small business and private entrepreneurship fast tumor provide, private property protection to do, entrepreneurship development on the way some administrative obstacles eliminate in our republic investment and entrepreneurship environment quality in terms of to a new stage raise through international to standards complete answer to give in providing own on the contrary finds

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Entrepreneurship of activity fast development to provide, private property each bilaterally protection to do and entrepreneurship environment quality in terms of to improve circle addition measures about the decree the president Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed. To him according to, small business and private of entrepreneurship fast development provide, private property protection to do and his inviolability guarantees strengthening, entrepreneurship in development bureaucratic obstacles eliminate in the republic investment and entrepreneurship environment improve in the eye caught. Small business and private to entrepreneurship wide freedom give, their to the activity state bodies intervention fundamentally reduction of offenses prevention to receive to provide, to offenses road not to be put entrepreneurship activities more development in the field state of politics important priority direction and state bodies the first level task reached it is called let it be marked in the document. Also in the decree it is said that from January 1, 2017 from, entrepreneurship subjects from the plan except of inspections all types void will be done. Control doer organs from this after from the plan except inspections transfer organize to do to the right have that it is not note done republic in the area small business and private entrepreneurship subjects number sharp to increase impulse it happened Today's in the day small business and private

entrepreneurship in the field being created wide opportunities this in the direction activity host subjects number sharp to increase reason is happening to information according to 2016 during total to the list received small business of enterprises the number is 16 thousand 208 organize reached is today in the day to the list received small business 91.3 percent of enterprises efficient activity showing is coming Our republic in the area economic in networks activity walking enterprises number, being created new the work seats with one in line they are by work being released products and their GDP in place more and more increased is going In particular, in 2000 gross internal of the product nearly 31 percent of the economy active developed going this sector per share right came if in 2005 this the indicator was 38.2 percent, 52.5 percent in 2010, 56.5 percent in 2015, 56.9 percent in 2016 organize this is it positive trend GDP 2000 of the volume compared to 25.9 units increased with is important.

According to official data, in 2019, the highest share of women in the total number of women in our Republic was in the cities of Tashkent (46.7%), Navoi (45.6%), Bukhara (45%) and Ferghana (44.2%), while the highest share of men was in Surkhandarya (65.1%, Kashkadarya (61.9%), Samarkand (61.2%), Jizzakh (60.4%) and Syrdarya (60.0%) provinces.

On the contrary, the largest number of cases was in Surkhandarya (34.9%), Kashkadarya (38.1%), Samarkand (38.8%) and Jizzakh (39.6%) provinces, while the lowest percentage of cases was in Tashkent city (53.3 %), Navoi (54.4%), Bukhara (55%), and Fergana (55.8%) provinces (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of employees by gender in the cross-section of regions

Table 1 shows that the number of people employed in the formal sector increased by 8.5% in 2020 compared to 2018 and by 8.2% compared to 2016. The number of people working in the informal sector decreased by 5.2% in 2020 compared to 2018. and increased by 0.6% compared to 2016. In 2020, the highest share of the population employed in the official sector in the total employment belongs to the regions of Tashkent city (81%), Navoi (67%), Tashkent (47.4%) and Bukhara (46.9%) came The highest rates of employment in the

informal sector are in Namangan (68.1%), Surkhandarya (67.8%), Samarkand (66.8%) and Kashkadarya (64.4%) provinces.

Distribution of employment by formal and informal sectors across regions

Table 1

	2016		2018		2020	
	officialy	nonofficial	officialy	nonofficial	official	nonofficial
Uzbekistan	40,5	59,5	39,1	60,9	42,3	57,7
Karakalpakstan	42,0	58,0	42,5	57,5	41,2	58,8
Andijan	33,2	66,8	31,2	68,8	36,3	63,7
Bukhara	38,9	61,1	41,3	58,7	46,9	53,1
Jizzakh	42,0	58,0	37,5	62,5	37,6	62,4
Kashkadarya	35,8	64,2	38,9	61,1	35,6	64,4
Navai	53,3	46,7	56,5	43,5	67,0	33,0
Namangan	32,9	67,1	29,7	70,3	31,9	68,1
Samarkand	34,4	65,6	32,2	67,8	33,2	66,8
Surkhandarya	40,6	59,4	32,2	67,8	32,2	67,8
Sirdarya	52,8	47,2	45,4	54,6	46,8	53,2
Tashkent	37,9	62,1	38,8	61,2	47,4	52,6
Fergana	39,0	61,0	34,4	65,6	35,9	64,1
Kharazm	38,3	61,7	34,4	65,6	37,2	62,8
Tashkent city	64,9	35,1	69,2	30,8	81,0	19,0

Today's in the day small business and entrepreneurship subjects financial support in order to fund by surety and compensation in the form of financial aids giving is coming. Only one past year during 20,258 small business and entrepreneurship of subjects commerce from banks received 33.208 billion. soum loans according to fund by 6.993 billion. soum amount financial obligations received.

- commercial banks by separable loans on 5356 small business and entrepreneurship to subjects 4,172 billion of the fund. soum in quantity surety obligations obtained as a result of the fund from the surety user small business and entrepreneurship subjects the number is 4.2 times higher than in 2019 increased;

- commercial banks loans according to percentage expenses to cover for of the fund compensation to give in the form of financial from the help used small business and entrepreneurship subjects the number and 14,902 have reached and The fund is 2,821 billion. soum amount percentage expenses to cover on the surface obligations received, as a result compared to 2019 compensation receivers the number is 4.4 times and pay to be given percentage expenses amount by 3.3 times increased common to volume relatively 2018-2022 years small and medium business.

Small business and private of entrepreneurship share. Table 2

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
GDP	62,4	56,0	55,7	54,9	50,5

Industry	37,4	25,8	27,9	27,0	23,2
Construction	73,2	75,8	72,5	72,4	74,9
Employment	76,3	76,2	74,5	74,4	74,8
Export	27,2	27,0	20,5	22,3	17,6
Import	56,2	61,6	51,7	48,7	44,7

In our country private of the owners rights and legal interests protection, entrepreneurship of subjects to the activity unreasonable from interventions reliable legal guarantees provided giving strong legislation base was created.

525 thousand in our country more than entrepreneurship subject activity is showing. Gross internal from 56 percent of the product more forming, to work capable from 78 percent of the population increase the work with providing small business and private entrepreneurship of subjects our country socio-political, socio-economic in development place and role more and more increased from going proof gives. Our country leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev by before Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 development five priority direction according to Actions in the strategy defined tasks execution including business field representatives and state organs in the middle efficient communication and useful cooperation mechanisms to the road put, private property and of entrepreneurship right and legal interests reliable protection to do guarantees strengthening, regions and in districts business environment improvement issues on, as well as entrepreneurship subjects, first of all, regions, cities and in districts good quality state services present to be done provide state organs and entrepreneurship structures mutually cooperation, especially entrepreneurship subjects activities now started in periods them of support new efficient system to create requirement is enough

Uzbekistan Republic President's decree of October 5, 2016 Entrepreneurship of activity fast development to provide, private property each bilaterally protection to do and businessmen environment quality in terms of to improve circle addition measures "about". Taxes in paragraph 5 of the decree and another mandatory payments collection expenses reduce, remote control wide current reach and tax of payers legal literacy which provides 584 increase tax administration quality and efficiency to improve separately attention directed.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Uzbekistan Republic State Statistics committee reference based on without we say possibly February 1,2022 to the situation according to activity showing small entrepreneurship subjects the number is 467,096 organize in 2017 suitable period with compared to 2.2 times increased Years in the section new organize done enterprises the number while in our republic january in the month new organize done enterprise and organizations number of 2017 suitable period with compared to 1.7 times increased. In our republic organizational and legal shape according to activity showing enterprises the number 3rd place family enterprises occupied and they are August 1, 2021 to the situation according to total entrepreneurship 10.9 percent of subjects share organize reached Summary in place to say preferably, small business and entrepreneurship in society social and economic in the fields there is problems solution in doing and of society socio-economic in development big role plays He worked output, work performance, service show in the fields new the work seats created the population the work with provide and unemployment in reduction

important importance occupation is enough In our republic small business and private entrepreneurship each bilaterally supporting them internal and external in the market compete good quality product work release and services to show consistent to the road sheep will receive strong economic to the field rotation provide it is necessary So since, the country in his life current and priority tasks performing field as small business and private entrepreneurship more developed, created wide of possibilities around use know, country development significant contribution to add in society there is has been all economic active of the population, moreover of all of us in front of us standing main task being will remain.

References:

1. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., Xasanboy, S. D., & Akmaljon o'g'li, A. X. (2022). ISH BILAN BANDLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TA'SIRI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 12(1), 4-10.
2. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., & Hasanboy o'g'li, S. D. (2022). Organization and increase of activity of small industrial zones.
3. Muhammadjonov, B. B. O. G. L., & Xudayberdiyev, O. A. (2022). O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KICHIK SANOAT HUDUDLARI RIVOJLANISHINING ISTIQBOLLARI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(1), 265-273.
4. O'G'LI, M. B. B. (2021). ESTABLISHMENT AND ACTIVITY OF SMALL FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN. International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences, 1(2), 156-159.
5. Abdullayevich, A. O., & Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2021, December). DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN. In Conference Zone (pp. 123-128).
6. Хакимов, Б., Талабоев, Х., & Холмирзаев, У. (2021). ВОПРОСЫ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ АНАЛИЗА ОБРАЩЕНИЯ ДОЛГОВОЙ ЗАДОЛЖЕННОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ. Экономика и социум, (6-2), 441-446.
7. Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2022, March). THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY. In Conference Zone (pp. 271-276).
8. Shodiyeva, G., Tog'Ayeva, D. A., & Sultonov, B. A. (2022). KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O 'RNI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(5), 610-613.
9. Мухитдинов, Ш. З. (2018). РОСТ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА НА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ И В ФЕРМЕРСКИХ ХОЗЯЙСТВАХ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН. ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ АПК. In XLVII INTERNATIONAL CORRESPONDENCE SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY" (pp. 52-54).
10. Mukhitdinov, S. Z. (2021). COVID-19 PANDEMIA IN UZBEKISTAN AGRICULTURE AND ITS IMPACT ON THE SUPPLY CHAIN. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 2(01), 177-183.